
Production of Solid Biofuel from Cashew Nut Shell

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ABSTRACT

In the face of global climate change and the lingering concerns over scarce fossil fuel supplies, the need for renewable and sustainable energy alternative is now an urgent priority. This research paper looks at production of solid biofuel or briquettes from cashew nutshells which can be used domestically. It strives towards producing a cheap, affordable and eco-friendly fuel source considering the recent surge in the price of petroleum products in Nigeria due to fuel subsidy removal. The cashew nutshell was collected washed, dried and manually separated from the kernel without roasting to keep the chemical components intact. It was dried again and grinded to increase the surface area to volume ratio. Its oil was extracted and a binding agent was added and it was moulded into pellets. The binding agent used was made from gasoline and Styrofoam. Afterwards various parameters were tested to keep track of the fuel properties.

Keywords: Solid biofuel, Cashew nut shell, Biomass energy, Renewable energy, Biofuel production

1.0 INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background of Study

The search for a more efficient biofuel has become an unending quest since its advantage over fossil fuel came to light, this is because we are in an era marked by mounting concerns over climate change, energy security, and scarce fossil fuel reserves. Biofuels derived from biomass offer a better chance of mitigating greenhouse gas emissions and achieving a more environmentally friendly energy landscape (Erans *et al.*, 2022).

It is important to note that biofuels present an appealing and viable option for renewable energy, in contrast to the geopolitical uncertainties, limited availability, and harmful global consequences associated with fossil fuel energy (Kour *et al.*, 2019).

Biofuels encompass a wide range of feedstock, conversion technologies, and end products, presenting a dynamic landscape for exploration. First-generation biofuels, such as ethanol produced from corn or sugarcane, have been in commercial use for many years, albeit with some limitations (Sikarwar & Zhao., 2017). However, recent efforts have focused on developing advanced biofuels, which utilize non-food crops, agricultural residues, and waste materials, minimizing the competition between food and fuel production while maximizing resource efficiency (Milano *et al.*, 2016).

One important factor to think about when assessing biofuels is how they affect the environment. Although biofuels could help decrease greenhouse gas emissions compared to traditional fuels, it's crucial to look at the entire process of making biofuels from growing the raw materials to using the fuel to make sure they're sustainable overall (Friedlingstein *et al.*, 2019).

Additionally, the economic viability and commercial scalability of biofuel production are crucial factors for its widespread adoption.

2.0 Literature Review

2.1 Solid Biofuels

Solid biofuels are derived from biomass sources like sawdust, agricultural residues including cashew nut shells, etc. The production process of solid biofuels may include the following stages:

1. Collection and processing of raw materials.
2. Mixing with binders.
3. Compressing into desired shapes.
4. Drying to remove excess moisture.

2.2 Advantages of Solid Biofuels

Solid biofuels offer several advantages such as:

1. Improved combustion
2. Flexibility
3. Energy density
4. Environmental friendliness

2.2.1 Improved Combustion

Solid biofuels can be engineered to possess enhanced combustion qualities, increasing their efficiency in comparison to conventional biomass materials.

2.2.2 Flexibility

Solid biofuels offer flexibility in terms of application. It can be used in a variety of applications including power generation, heating and cooking.

2.2.3 Energy Density

Solid biofuels have a higher energy density than traditional biomass materials, making them more efficient for transportation and storage.

2.2.4 Environmental Friendliness

Solid biofuels are more environmental friendly when compared to fossil fuels. They emit less amount of greenhouse gases.

2.3 Production Processes for Solid Biofuels

There are several processes used in the production of solid biofuels. Some of these processes are as follows:

1. Briquetting
2. Pelleting
3. Torrefraction

2.3.1 Briquetting

This is the process of converting loose biomass materials into a compact dense and uniform fuel product called briquettes (Yunusa *et al.*, 2023). Various biomass may require a pre-treatment process before briquetting for example, if the biomass contains oil, the oil may be extracted before briquetting. Also, some biomass may contain substances that may be environmentally hazardous when burnt, for instance sulphur. Such toxic substances may be separated.

2.3.2 Pelleting

This is a process of converting fine loose biomass materials into a dense uniform and compact fuel product called pellets. The process involves:

1. Collection and processing of biomass materials.
2. Grinding the materials into a fine powder.
3. Mixing with binders.
4. Feeding the mixture into a pellet mill
5. Extruding the mixture through a die to form pellets.
6. Cutting the pellets to a uniform length.
7. Cooling and drying the pellets.

2.3.3 Torrefraction

Torrefraction is a process that involves the heating of biomass, typically to the range of 200-300°C, in the absence of oxygen to produce a dry robust and energy-dense fuel (Djurdjevic & Papuga, 2023). The process involves the following:

1. Collecting the biomass materials
2. Heating the material to release water and volatile matter.
3. Cooling and drying the materials
4. Densification

3.0 MATERIALS AND METHOD

3.1 Materials

1. Cashew seed
2. Styrofoam based binding agent.

3. Distilled water

3.2 Method

3.2.1 Cashew Nut Shell Biofuel Preparation

The seed of the cashew was obtained within Makurdi, Benue state, Nigeria. The quantity was 15kg. It was washed and pre-dried. The kernel of the seed was separated from the seed manually, it was crushed and the kernel was removed without roasting the seed as traditionally done by cashew nut sellers. The reason is to keep the chemical components of the seed intact because once it undergoes combustion in full supply of oxygen, it may no longer serve its purpose. It was washed again a second time and was then blended using a blender. The oil was extracted. It was then dried and weighed in an oven at a low temperature of about 35 degrees Celsius. During the drying process, the weight was checked every two hours until a constant weight was obtained.

It was then heated in the absence of air in a furnace (L1/12-LT 40/12). The oil was further separated after this heating process.

Styrofoam based binder was added and it was converted it into briquettes. At this point it is ready for use. Its fuel potential and properties were tested in a controlled environment.

Fig. 1.0: Process Flow Diagram

3.2.2 Binding Agent Preparation

The binding agent was prepared by dissolving 950g of chips of Styrofoam in 50cl of gasoline. It was continuously stirred using a stirrer until it was completely dissolved. It was stored in glass bottles.

3.2.3 Fuel Property Tests

The fuel properties of the solid biofuel were determined using Proximate analysis. Proximate analysis is a standardized laboratory procedure used to determine the approximate composition of a fuel sample, such as coal, biomass, or briquettes (solid biofuel). The procedure involves a series of tests to quantify the following components:

1. Moisture Content (MC)
2. Volatile Matter (VM)
3. Ash Content (AC)

Moisture Content (MC)

2 grams of the sample was weighed using a crucible, it was dried in an oven (XL300T) at 100-110°C (212-230°F) for 1-2 hours. It was then allowed to cool and it was reweighed. The moisture content was calculated as a percentage of the original weight.

$$\text{Percent Moisture Content} = \frac{\text{Original Weight} - \text{Weight after heating}}{\text{Original Weight}} \times 100\%$$

Volatile Matter (VM)

2 grams of a fresh sample of the cashew nut shell solid biofuel was weighed. It was placed on a crucible and heated to a temperature of 950 degrees celsius (1742°F) in a furnace (L1/12-LT 40/12) for 10 minutes and allowed to cool and it was reweighed. The volatile matter was calculated as a percentage of the original weight.

$$\text{Percent Volatile Matter} = \frac{\text{Weight of volatile matter}}{\text{Original Weight}} \times 100\%$$

Ash Content (AC)

2g of a fresh sample was weighed and Placed in a crucible. It was heated in a furnace ((L1/12-LT 40/12)) at 500Degrees Celsius (932°F) for 2 hours. It was allowed to cool and reweighed.

The ash content was calculated as a percentage of the original weight.

$$\text{Percent Ash Content} = \frac{\text{Weight of Ash}}{\text{Original Weight}} \times 100\%$$

Testing for the Heating Value

An isothermal calorimeter (S1341) was used to test for the heating value of the cashew nut shell. It is a precise instrument used to measure the heat of combustion of materials, including biomass.

A precise amount of 2 grams was weighed. The calibrated isothermal calorimeter was set to desired temperature of 25 Degrees Celsius. The weighed cashew nut shell was placed into a crucible and loaded into the calorimeter's sample holder. A small amount of ignition source (benzoic acid) was introduced into the sample container. Combustion was initiated by heating the ignition source with a flame or electric spark.

The calorimeter measured the heat evolved during combustion, maintaining a constant temperature. The heat is absorbed by the calorimeter's surroundings, and the temperature change is monitored.

The heat absorbed (in joules or calories) over a specified time period was recorded until the reaction was complete; this was indicated by a stable temperature reading. The heat of combustion (Q) in joules per gram (J/g) was calculated using the following formula:

$$Q = \frac{\text{Heat absorbed}}{\text{Sample mass}}$$

The procedure was repeated times to ensure accuracy and precision. The result was averaged to obtain a reliable value for the heating value of the cashew nut shell solid biofuel.

4.0 Results and Discussion

4.1 Cashew Nut Shell Characterization Result

Fig. 2.0 SEM for cashew nut shell

Sample	: Cashewnut	File	: Sg2~1.ASC	Date	: June 14 9:50:34	Operator	:
Comment	: Qualitative	Memo					
Method	: 2nd differential	Typical width	: 0.065 deg.	Min. Height		400:00 c p s	

Fig 3.0 XRD for cashew nut shell

Fig. 4.0 FTIR for cashew nut shell

Table 1: Results from Fuel Property Tests

Ash Content %	Carbon Content%	Volatile Matter%	Heating Value J/g
2.3	82	70	19.5

4.2 Discussion of Results

The cashew nut shell solid biofuel (CNSSB) has a heating value of 19.5. This implies that it has a significant energy potential, which can be harnessed for various applications. The heating value is comparable to other biomass used for fuel such as wood chips. It also showed a volatile matter content of 70%, this implies that it can easily be ignited. The carbon content of the CNSSB was 82%. This shows that it can also be utilized for other energy applications, chemical synthesis and material development.

5.0 Conclusion

Cashew nut shell solid biofuel is a viable alternative domestic fuel with good fuel properties. The shells are wastes from processing of cashew nut. The crop is readily available and can be used for this purpose. Like every other biofuel, it causes less pollution than fossil fuels.

6.0 Recommendation

Due to present increase in price of petroleum products currently in Nigeria, it is highly recommended that the cashew nut shell solid biofuel be adopted as an alternative source of fuel because it is cheap and easy to produce. The main starting materials, cashew nut shell and Styrofoam are both wastes.

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